

CoARA Action Plan 2025-2029

Organization	Corvinus University of Budapest
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1. Background

Corvinus University of Budapest (hereinafter: Corvinus) signed the Agreement on **Reforming Research Assessment** (ARRA) and joined the **Coalition for Advancing Research Assessment** (CoARA) in June 2023. That month Corvinus has become a member of CoARA Hungarian National Chapter as well.

Corvinus embraces all the principles and commitments of the Agreement. This action plan outlines the major steps Corvinus will take to develop and harmonise its research evaluation practices with the principles of CoARA.

2. Existing frameworks:

Academic Career Model, Research Strategy, Institutional Development Plan

The **Academic Career Model (ACM)** was introduced at the beginning of 2021 at Corvinus. The primary aim of the introduction of the Career Model was to strengthen Corvinus' international competitiveness by improving the research and teaching performance of the faculty and by strengthening the quality focus in all academic areas.

The 3-year-cycle of the Academic Career Model makes conscious planning and predictability of academic careers and promotion possible, allowing the academic faculty to contribute to the strategic goals of Corvinus, by choosing a **balanced**, a **teaching focused**, or a **research focused** job type, according to their academic performance and personal academic ambitions.

Annual performance target setting and development plans, their annual review and a triennial comprehensive performance review secures a regular monitoring of the fulfilment of individual goals, compliance, and performance evaluation, while supporting the individual career development as a positive incentive. The chosen career path is valid for a 3-year cycle, but it can be changed for the next period if professional ambitions change. The ACM includes career consulting for colleagues who are preparing for promotion, along a clear system of requirements.

The performance evaluation aspects focus on the fulfilment of the quantitative and qualitative requirements, considering the following key principles:

Legality The designation of teaching and research positions that can be created in Hungarian higher education institutions and, in certain cases, the requirements related to them are defined in Act CCIV of 2011 on National Higher Education.

International compatibility For each job, the career model defines the employment requirements and the expectations regarding performance to make them attractive and understandable for the international academic labour market.

Excellence in an academic sense will always be based on a lasting, regular, and high-quality performance (research excellence, teaching excellence, service excellence).

Diversity is the source of creativity and the basis of innovative thinking towards excellence, a value that appears also in the career model of Corvinus.

Transferability An academic career is a stage of an individual's life that lasts for different periods, sometimes including (multiple) exits and entries.

Merits In the academic career model, meritocracy plays a central role.

Equal treatment The career model places particular emphasis on ensuring that the social roles that influence women's academic careers (such as having and raising children) are taken into account when assessing job types and job classifications.

Transparency An important element of the career model is that any difference between the base salaries of employees employed in the same lecturer-researcher positions and job types is generated solely by transparent performance.

Employment conditions, and incentives It is an important feature of the academic career model that it does not only set expectations but also encourages their realization through various means.

The Academic Senate of Corvinus approved its **Research Strategy** in January 2024, as a functional strategy of the Institutional Development Plan (2024-2027). The document sets the priorities, objectives, and actions Corvinus eager to follow in the 2024-2027 period.

The key targets of research strategy are

to support the **development of the scientific skills** of its researchers,

to strengthen its **international scientific embeddedness** of Corvinus by making research career more attractive for PhD students and young colleagues, and

to strengthen the **competitiveness of doctoral students**, and

to improve **the quality and the scientific/economic/social impacts** of scholarly contributions.

Finally, the Institutional Development Plan 2025-2028 (“The Bridge Strategy”) was approved by the Senate and the Board of Trustees in June 2025. The strategy emphasizes transforming Corvinus into a **research-driven institution** that strengthens **international collaboration** and **visibility**. It aims to enhance research performance through initiatives such as revising the Academic Career Model, attracting top-tier faculty, and creating clear pathways for academic growth. The plan includes launching a comprehensive PhD and Teaching Assistant program to cultivate future scholars, alongside establishing cutting-edge research centers.

The CoARA Action Plan is in line with the ACM, the Research Strategy, and the Institutional Development Plan.

3. Organization

The actions on reforming research assessment practices at Corvinus will be coordinated by **CoARA Working Group** with members from

Faculty and Research Management,

University Library and Archives,

Centre for Grants and Projects, and

the Research Committee.

The actions will be executed under the guidance of the Vice-Rector for Faculty and Research, and the working group will report to the Vice-Rector for Faculty and Research.

4. Objectives

By joining CoARA, Corvinus commits to the core principles of ARRA. This section provides an overview of the main objectives Corvinus set to achieve during the **renewal of its research assessment practices**:

review existing processes in relation to the assessment of quality and impact of research at the level of individual researchers, institutes, departments, and research centres,

formulate principles for the responsible use of research metrics in research assessment,

develop and implement the **mechanisms of qualitative research evaluation**,

provide **training and support for colleagues** doing research assessment,

communicate progress and results of the renewal process within the Corvinus community, and

evaluate the results of renewal process at the end of the reform period (2030).

5. Actions

Corvinus will take the following steps to achieve its objectives related to the renewal of research evaluation practices until the end of 2030:

Phase	Action	Timeframe	Description
Phase I	Establishment of CoARA Working Group at Corvinus	2025 Q4	Set up working group for the elaboration, implementation and monitoring of the COARA Action Plan. Establishment of regular follow-up meetings
	Participation in WGs and National Chapter	2025 Q4 – <i>as long as WGs are active</i>	Actively participate in the following CoARA working groups: Ethics and Research Integrity Policy Evaluating Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) Research Globally Multilingualism and Language Biases in Research Assessment Reforming Academic Career Assessment Responsible Metrics and Indicators Thinking Critically about University Rankings Towards Transformations: Transdisciplinarity, Applied/Practice-Based Research, and Impacts Actively participate in the Hungarian National Chapter
	Communication and dissemination	2025 Q4 – 2029 Q4	Continuously communicate about the transformation process
Phase II	Gap analysis	2026 Q1	Analyse our current institutional practices in research evaluation Identify possible areas for improvement and obstacles to address in relation to the fulfilment of CoARA principles
	Policy revision	2026 Q3	Revise the existing regulatory documents to reflect gap analysis outcomes
Phase III	Development of new assessment systems	2026 Q4	Develop alternative evaluation practices to replace or complement the existing ones

Phase IV	Implementation: pilot project	2027 Q1 – Q4	Implement a small-scale research evaluation project using the approaches developed in previous phase
	Collecting feedbacks	2027 Q1 – Q4	Gather input from the implementation of pilot project
Phase V	Global implementation	2028 Q1 – 2029 Q2	Apply the revised evaluation protocols in all research assessment processes
	Revision of research assessment processes	2029 Q3 – Q4	Comprehensively revise and adjust the research assessment processes

In implementing the action plan, we will incorporate the relevant best practices of other CoARA members and involve the entire Corvinus research community to ensure the success of the research culture change process.

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